

A Critical Appraisal of the Researches in Philosophy of Education in the Last Two Decades

Swami Tattwasarananda

Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math.
E-mail: swamitattwasarananda@gmail.com

ABSTRACT : Philosophy of education has been considered to be the disciplined study of philosophical issues arising in ideas, practices and policies relevant to education. In the present paper an attempt has been made to appraise critically the trends of researches in philosophy of education in the last two decades

Keywords : Philosophy of education, Critical appraisal.

Philosophy of education as a unique type of educational inquiry

Generally speaking, philosophy of education has been considered to be the disciplined study of philosophical issues arising in ideas, practices and policies relevant to education (White, 2009). Though, philosophy of education is often assumed – from outside the discipline – to be a matter of articulating definition of complex concepts, of providing a personal manifesto or a social group's shared educational ideas, of reflecting on one of a number of rival schools of thought or 'isms', such as existentialism or phenomenology, or perhaps, of pondering over the grand reflective wisdom of great thinkers,

such as Plato, John Dewey or Swami Vivekananda. As a preliminary indication, it (philosophy of education) should be assumed to be a distinctive type of educational inquiry setting out to throw light on the deeper meaning and aims of education in its multidimensional context. Furthermore, that line of educational inquiry had to have involved analyzing arguments, identifying and probing assumptions, assessing claims, clarifying concepts and what not!

If it be treated as a branch of practical philosophy, the practitioners of philosophy of education look both inward to the parent discipline of philosophy and at the same time outward to the ongoing educational practices,

as well as to developmental psychology, cognitive science, sociology and other relevant disciplines and approaches in a more general way (Sigel, 2009). Now, a useful way to distinguish between philosophical and other approaches to educational inquiry is, by taking into account, the distinction between first and second order of questions and discourses. In education, the first order discourses could comprise everyday talk concerning actual classroom practices or policy discussion with regard to educational situations and issues. For example, we can select a call for education to be inclusive. But, on the other, the second order philosophical discourse would focus on the concept of inclusion differently, reflecting on it to develop a critical discourse that tries to clarify the concept of inclusion and similarly complex, related concepts – to scrutinize assumptions and arguments concerning them and to develop a sound critique on the issue of inclusion keeping it at the backdrop of experiences gained in the real classroom situation and therefore, as a natural consequence through the policy discussions (Enslin, 2010).

The contribution of philosophy to educational research - Western paradigm

According to some western scholars, the nature of educational research in philosophy of education itself points to three kinds of contribution which philosophy can and does to this endeavour (Bridges, 2010).

First, philosophy itself is among those erudite, orderly and unrelenting disciplines which can be drawn upon to contribute to educational inquiry. This is philosophy as educational research. For example, we cannot go far in the consideration of educational policies and practices without being engaged in the fundamental questions

about the aims of education and the values and principles which ought to govern these policies and practices. And again, we can't go far in pursuit of social-justice agenda in education without countering contested interpretations of social justice and conflicts with other social principles and values. Thus, there are certain major educational issues which are to be illustrated, analyzed, investigated and discussed in the long tradition of philosophical inquiry. Here, philosophy itself emerges as an educational research.

Second, the claims and limitations of all of the other forms of enquiry which offer contributions to educational research need to be examined and understood, and this is philosophical work of an epistemological character rooted in the theory of knowledge. Thus, in recently prevailing western paradigms, this is also referred to as philosophy of educational research.

Third, any research which required engagement with human participants and the redistribution of their knowledge that raises issues of an ethical and political character which have their roots in a long standing tradition of philosophical ethics and socio-political philosophy.

Without having entered into the intricacies of the 'methodological rigour question' involved in the researches in the west during the last two decades, ample evidences can be cited from among the researches in philosophy of education which in some way or other, belong to any one of the above three categories.

The following list (Seshadri, 2006) of topic gives one an impression of kind of problems that have engaged philosophers of education in the

English speaking world and thus have been able to keep it as a vibrant field of academic activity:

- i) Caring as a democratic virtue.
- ii) Social constructivism and mathematics education
- iii) Universal values and particular identities in anti-racist education.
- iv) Four philosophical perspectives on school inspection.
- v) Integrating philosophies of mind and of education
- vi) Habermas and the tension between authority and democracy in education.

The International Encyclopedia of Education, 2010 can provide many more examples of such studies which endeavour to relate researches in philosophy of education to educational practices in the society as well as policy planning of a particular nation.

An appraisal of the Indian case

To start with the Indian experiences of researches in philosophy of education, the most reliable literatures, which for us are easily accessible and with which we have been able to become familiar, are the surveys of educational research, published by the NCERT and in almost all the survey reports, we may give a large attention to one writer, namely C. Seshadri, mainly because his observations perfectly suit the purpose of this paper. As Seshadri has observed, “at one time, philosophy of education enjoyed the status of a subject of study in its own right in teacher preparatory programmes....When the educational theory package in teacher education programmes came under review from the point of view of relevance

it was thought that an interdisciplinary course which combined functional segments from the foundational disciplines would meet the needs of the students better. The result of this approach to de-emphasize educational theory per se was that, philosophy of education as an intellectual discipline lost its place...” (Seshadri, 2006). In the fourth survey of educational research, Seshadri had lamented over the depressing state of affairs that characterized research studies in philosophy of education, such as a highly restricted paradigm with ‘study of educational philosophy/ ideas/ contributions of....’ types of researches virtually defining the domain of the field; lack of methodological rigour; philosophical indifference to ongoing educational happenings; an almost pathological obsession with the past and absence of enterprise to explore the new or ‘here and now’. After a lapse of five years in the fifth survey, he (Seshadri) felt dismayed that not only had there been no visible improvement in the overall situation but also that the quality of the output during the intervening years had deteriorated further. Keeping all these harsh comments in mind, NCTE’s recent initiative to proliferate the revision in B.Ed. as well as M.Ed. curriculum the ‘philosophical foundation of education’ portion in the consecutive names ‘development of education’, ‘education as a field of study’ and ‘process of education’ seems to be quite symbolic to the disappointed depiction in the field of researches in philosophy of education in India!

In the fifth survey (1988-92), the 38 studies which had been classified as philosophy of education research include studies of different types and foci (Seshadri, 1997). The leading category had been the study of the educational philosophy/ contributions of individual thinkers/ philosophical schools, scriptures, historical/

cultural periods etc. Nearly 70% of researches (26) account for this type. Rests are studies that focus on educational/ philosophical themes account for the remaining. This variety, as just been portrayed, are in full conformity with the trodden path showed in the previous surveys as regards the researches in philosophy of education. Studies appeared to be repetitive also. On Sri Aurobindo alone there had been five research studies, others who continued to enjoy favouritism were Gandhi (4), Krishnamurti (2), Vedas and Upanishads (2) and Tagore (1). The new 'educational philosophers' figuring then were Vinoba Bhave, Dolararai Mankad, Samartha Ramdas, Ram Tirth, Manubhai Pancholi, Sane Guruji, Vidya Sagar, Radhakrishnan, Rajendra Prasad and Sri Ma. While most of the thinkers had been studied individually and their ideas explored with reference to current educational situation, Aurobindo was studied in a comparative frame with Tagore, Gandhi, Rousseau (separate studies); the Upanishads with Vivekananda; Radhakrishnan with Russel; and Sri Ma with Plato. Thus, broadly speaking, researches produced in fifth as well as sixth (only ten in number) surveys fall into the following three types:

Type 1: Biographical studies i.e. the studies of the educational philosophy/ thoughts/ ideas/ practices of individual thinkers/ systems.

Type 2: Thematic studies.

Type 3: Comparative studies.

According to Seshadri, excepting a few ones, most of the studies suffered from the following quandaries in some way or other:

i) In most cases mere collection and

compilation of the ideas and thoughts of a thinker had been the aim of the researcher, though it would not amount to philosophy in its true spirit. The researchers in the field are always expected to present a coherent and consistent account of the ideas.

- ii) It appeared even more disturbing to Seshadri that a researcher saw an educational philosopher in any one who has had something or other to say about education.
- iii) Most of the studies went in the name of comparative study had been deficient in a clearly conceived and well defined frame of reference.
- iv) Excepting a few ones, most of the studies lacked in semantic clarity, meaningfulness, consistency, consciousness of assumptions as well as methodological awareness.

Epilogue

Thus, as against the pulsating state of affairs in researches in philosophy of education in the English speaking world during the last two decades, the scene in India has been indeed dismal and previously an attempt had been made somewhere to trace out the causes of such a depressing state of affairs that characterized research studies in philosophy of education (Tattwasarananda, 2009). For remedying such a depressing state a, deeper level of understanding of the aims and objectives of the research project followed by a rigorous methodological precision which tends to be free from ambiguity and which will be made to remain open to addition, alteration, modification and even zero audit may kindle hope in the

present situation in India and this new paradigm may restore to philosophy of education its rightful place for which we had always been proud of. For mounting a brilliant paradigm and to furnish a new direction the researchers in the said field are to be prepared to answer to the following queries:

1. Can the plethora of national schemes and projects relating to pre-school and elementary education, secondary education, vocational education, teacher education, adult education and higher education floated in the initial flush of education policies be not made subject to philosophical inquiry?
2. Can it not raise important issues like democracy, equality, secularism, freedom, fundamental rights, authority and autonomy, social justice etc. having relevance for education and tackle them philosophically – offering arguments, clarifying concepts, putting forward metaphysical views with intellectual support and offering grounds for normative assertions?
3. Can the methodologies employed in the researches in philosophy of education itself not be worth researching?

4. Instead of being referred to the category of Psychology of education, can the archeology of knowledge not be put under scrutiny in the name of philosophy of education?

References

- Bridges, D. (2010), Philosophy and Educational Research, In P. Peterson, E. Baker and B. McGaw (Ed.), International Encyclopedia of Education, Vol. VI, Academic Press, USA.
- Enslin, P. (2010), Philosophy of Education, In P. Peterson, E. Baker and B. McGaw (Ed.), International Encyclopedia of Education, Vol. VI, Academic Press, USA.
- Siegel, H. (2009), Introduction: Philosophy of Education and Philosophy, In H. Siegel (Ed.), The Oxford Handbook of Philosophy of Education, OUP.
- Seshadri, C. (1991). Research in Philosophy of Education – A Trend Report, In M. B. Buch (Ed.), Fifth survey of Research in education (1983 – 88), Vol.-1, NCERT.
- Seshadri, C. (2006). Philosophy of Education, In M. B. Buch (Ed.), Sixth Survey of Research in education (1993 – 2000), Vol.-1, NCERT.
- Tattwasarananda, S. (2009)., Quest for a new paradigm in the researches in philosophy of education in India in the postmodern era, In *Sikshachintan*, A Journal of Education (ISSN 0973 5461), Vol – 3, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, West Bengal.
- White, J. (2008), Philosophy of Education, In Gary McCulloch & David Crook (Ed.), The Routledge International Encyclopedia of Education, Routledge, New York and London.

Received : 15th February, 2011

Accepted : 15th July, 2011